
Study Practices of the Students of Higher Secondary (10+2) Schools

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Abstract

The study habits of higher secondary school students are investigated in this work. The nature of the Study is inclusive and descriptive. One hundred higher secondary school students from the Muzaffarpur district made up the sample, which was chosen using the stratified random sampling technique. The researcher employed Mukhopadhyay Sansanwal's (2011) Study Habits Inventory as a method for gathering data. The Study's main conclusions were that (i) Higher secondary school students attending private and public schools had significantly different mean study habit scores, and (ii) Higher secondary school students attending male and female schools had significantly different mean study habit scores.

Keywords: Government and Private Schools, Higher Secondary Schools, Study Habits, Male, Female

Introduction

Global competition is becoming more intense. Performance attributes are now the primary criterion for personal growth. On the performance ladder, parents want their child to reach the most incredible level attainable. The pressure to achieve at high levels is enormous for students, teachers, schools, and the educational system. The entire educational system is geared around students' academic performance, even though the system is also expected to provide a variety of other outcomes. As a result, the school invests a lot of time and money in helping students improve their academic standing. Scholars in education have brought up important questions about the value of academic achievement (Ramaswamy, 1990). What factors support kids' academic success? To what extent can you measure each factor's impact on academic achievement? The keys to better learning and academic performance in schools are excellent teachers, a supportive home environment, a demanding curriculum, parental involvement, first-rate textbooks, and—most importantly—student study habits (Robinson, 2000).

The actions students take to organize their time and surroundings for

deliberate study activity are collectively referred to as study habits. In order to properly study a subject, a student must be able to categorize, arrange, and put information in the appropriate perspective. Study habits are "the students' manner of studying, whether systematic, effective, or inefficient, etc." according to Good (1973). We call these actions that students do to improve their learning during the learning process "good study habits."

According to Nuthana and Yenagi (2009), the purpose of study habits is to elicit and guide a student's cognitive process during their studies. Patel (1976) stated that effective study habits should consider the following: preparation for tests, general attitudes and habits, work-planning habits, reading and note-taking habits, subject-planning habits, concentration habits, and the educational environment. Nonetheless, a student's educational history, encompassing their coursework in the humanities, sciences, and other disciplines, may be considered.

According to the literature, students can enhance their learning outcomes by adopting suitable study habits (Kaur, 2005; Singla, 2007). Studies by Gakhar Bains 2011, Rajakumar & Soundararajan 2012, Chand 2013, and Promila 2014 have shown that a variety of demographic factors, including gender, residential background, academic stream, family type (nuclear or joint), school type (government or private), and parental education, influence the study habits of

adolescents enrolled in higher secondary schools. The findings revealed no appreciable variations in the general and particular study habits of secondary school students from nuclear and mixed families. Regarding living arrangements, workload scheduling, and subject planning, secondary school students attending public schools outperform those attending private schools significantly. However, concerning study habits and test preparation, private school students outperform public school students significantly. Regarding their study habits, female students in the arts and sciences did better than male students (Promila, 2016). Dhankher's 2016 study, however, did not discover any statistically significant variations in the study habits of IX-grade students based on their geography, gender, school management, or parental education.

Over the past 30 years, more than 400 global assessments have recommended changes to how parents and educators instruct our children (Hawley, 2002; Hurd, 1994; NRC, 1996). These studies emphasize how important it is for students—especially those in higher secondary schools—to develop good study habits.

The rationale of the Study

Students enrolled in higher secondary schools are developing during their teenage years. In essence, we live in a dynamic period of rapid progress and transformation. Academic failure can lead to frustration and a lack of adaptation. Without efficient time

management, topic weighting, note-taking, and subject-specific preparation techniques, even a capable student with the potential to perform better may not be able to live up to expectations. Put differently, an individual's study habits are relevant when evaluating their academic achievement.

Parents will be able to interact with their children more effectively and understand the importance of healthy study habits for academic success, according to this Study. Using this knowledge, the teachers may create a more caring, peaceful, friendly, and democratic environment at the school and encourage students to develop healthy study habits. Teachers might also help students modify their behavior about their study habits in light of the Study's findings. The goal of the research was to learn more about how to help students in higher secondary schools develop productive study habits in order to prepare them for academic achievement.

Objectives of the Study

1. To compare the average study habits scores of higher secondary school students attending private and public schools.
2. To compare the average study habits scores of higher secondary school students in the genders.

Hypothesis of the Study

1. The mean study habits scores of higher secondary school students attending government and private schools do not significantly differ from one another.

2. There is no discernible difference between male and female higher secondary school students' mean study habits scores.

Research Methodology

The Study is descriptive-survey in nature.

Sample of the Study

The sample was chosen using a stratified random sampling technique from the senior secondary schools in the Muzaffarpur district. One hundred students from class XI, fifty of them male and fifty of them female, made up the sample.

Tools of the Study

The researcher evaluated the study habits of senior secondary students using the Mukhopadhyay and Sansanwal (2011) study habits inventory method.

Statistical Analysis

To statistically treat the data, the t-test, mean, and S.D. were used.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Objective 1:

"To compare mean scores of study habits of government and private senior secondary school students" is the first objective. Data was evaluated using the t-test, mean, and standard deviation to accomplish this goal. The resulting outcomes are displayed as follows in Table 1:

Table 1: This table compares the study habits of senior secondary school students attending public and private schools

Variable	Locality	N	Mean	S.D.	df	t-value	Level of significance
Study Practices	Government	50	35.40	10.95	98	2.35	0.05
	Private	50	36.50	12.3			

Fig.1: This figure compares the study patterns of senior secondary school students attending public and private schools.

The study habits of senior secondary school students attending public and private schools are contrasted in Table 1. Table 1 shows that the t-value is 2.35, significant at the 0.05 level, with a df of 98. It indicates a significant difference in the mean study habits scores between senior secondary

school students attending government and private schools. As a result, the null hypothesis—which states that there is no discernible difference between the mean study habits scores of senior secondary school students attending government and private schools—is rejected. Furthermore, government

senior secondary school students' mean study habits score is 35.4, whereas the mean score of private senior secondary school students is 36.5, a substantial difference. Thus, it may be concluded that senior secondary school students attending private schools had superior study habits compared to those attending public schools.

Objective 2:

"To compare mean scores of study habits of male and female senior secondary school students" is the second objective. Data was evaluated using the t-test, mean, and standard deviation to accomplish this goal. The resulting outcomes are displayed as follows in Table 2:

Table 2: Comparison of study patterns between male and female higher secondary school students

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	df	t-value	Level of significance
Study Practices	Male	50	42.49	18.3	98	2.21	0.05
	Female	50	50.70	20.5			

Fig. 2: This figure compares male and female higher secondary school students' study patterns.

The study habits of male and female senior secondary school students' compared in Table 2. Table 2 shows that the t-value is 2.21, significant at the 0.05 level, with a df of 98. It demonstrates the notable

differences in the mean study habits scores between male and female senior secondary school students. Consequently, the null hypothesis, which held that the mean study habits scores of male and female senior

secondary school students did not differ significantly, is rejected. Furthermore, compared to male senior secondary school students, whose mean study habits score is 42.49, female students' mean score 50.7 is much higher. Therefore, female students in their senior year of secondary school had superior study habits than their male counterparts.

Results of the Research

The Study's main conclusions are as follows:

1. Students attending government and private senior secondary schools differ significantly in their study habits. Regarding their study habits, students in private senior secondary schools outperform those in government schools.
2. The study habits of male and female students in their senior year of secondary school differ significantly. When compared to male senior secondary school students, female students had superior study habits.

Conclusions and Discussion

Based on the analysis of the findings of this investigation, the subsequent deductions have been made:

1. Considerable variations in the study habits of senior secondary school students have been noted depending on the kind of school, with private senior secondary schools showing the most disparities. Premalakshmi's (2012) study yielded the same findings,

indicating that private higher secondary school students have superior study habits to their government counterparts. According to a study by Yadav (2015), government school students have better study habits than those in private schools, which is in contrast to the findings of the current Study.

2. Considerable gender disparities in the study habits of senior secondary school students have been noted, with a preference for females. Research by Singh 2011, Promila (2014), and Sud & Sujata (2006) all found that female students in senior secondary schools have superior study habits than male students. According to studies by Singla (2007), Hasan & Rao (2012), Premalakshmi (2012), and Rajakumar & Soundararajan (2012), there are no appreciable differences between the study habits of male and female students. These findings run counter to the findings of the current Study.

The Study's Implications for Education

The current Study's findings indicate that students attending private senior secondary schools have superior study habits to those attending government senior secondary schools. One possible explanation could be that private schools offer superior resources and possibilities, including larger

classroom sizes, intelligent classrooms, libraries, well-equipped labs, and ICT use. Government senior secondary school teachers, principals, legislators, and administrators should ensure that their institutions have enough classroom space, a playground for physical education, well-stocked libraries, and well-equipped labs. These provisions will boost students' enthusiasm for learning and help them develop excellent study habits.

According to the Study, female students in senior secondary schools had better study habits than male students. This could be because females are more driven, competitive, and have superior interpersonal skills. To evaluate the cause of poor study habits and implement suitable methods to instill better study habits in boys, educators, parents, legislators, and administrators must collaborate

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